

DEVELOPING SPEECH ABILITY AMONG ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *One of the major difficulties in the English language for English language learners as a second language is considered to be the work on texts. Learners face to many problems such as: searching for new words, long pauses, repetitions and etc . The article has a useful effect on improving the working ability on texts and overcome the above-mentioned problems.*

Key words: *English language learners as a second language, instruction, factors of speech ability, point accuracy, clarity of speech, the content of the speech, correctness of speech.*

The positive processes that have taken place since the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the Law "On Education" and the "National Training Program" require the development of in-depth concepts of foreign language learning ^[1]. As a result, the education system pays special attention to the study of foreign languages by students, as well as the formation of a certain level of communication skills in a foreign language, the development of point culture in them. It is well known that the ability to speak is an important aspect of society and human development, and it is a process that requires constant research, aspiration and improvement.

The main factors of speech ability:

1. Point accuracy.
2. Clarity of speech.
3. The content of the speech
4. Grammatical correctness of speech

And most importantly, the speaker's self-confidence.

In the formation and development of students' oral speech, it is not enough to use methods such as questioning, memorizing literary texts, small poems, which are not completely obsolete, but they need to be modernized [2-27]. It is advisable to talk more in that language in order to develop oral communication in that language. Because a person learning a foreign language always feels a responsibility to learn a lot, his or her mental activity automatically completes the acceptance process. As a result, the practical application of speech development is inevitably overlooked due to the fact that it is limited to the reception. In order to develop oral speech, the learner's monologue and dialogic speech should be the focus. These two aspects of oral communication are a key part of achieving a goal. Of course, the teacher's speech plays an important role in this. In order for a teacher to achieve his or her goals, he or she must first be able to create that atmosphere among the learners [3-114]. Only when the learner is able to develop the ability to listen and comprehend will the chances of developing the ability to speak be high. Raising the level requires the learner to be able to draw a portrait and develop imagination. As we work to improve our speaking ability, we focus the learner's attention on meaningful words rather than on memorized or familiar combinations, linking those words together, and finally we need to find the main idea. Of course, it is difficult to complete this step without increasing the remaining 3 Listening-Listening, Reading-Reading, Writing-writing skills. In short, the learner needs to increase the vocabulary.

Based on the above and my personal experience, let's work together on one of the ways to improve oral communication:

- Choose any of the following 10 topics.
 1. Automobiles
 2. Travelling
 3. Environment
 4. Tourism

5. TV program
 6. Work and study
 7. Children and adults
 8. Hobbies and leisure
 9. Tradition
 10. Physical training
- Make a list of meaningful words related to your chosen topic
 - Match the words in your list.

Note: In this small practice, we focused on 3 important points;

- Focus on meaningful words
- Characterization of mental reading
- Connect meaningful words

Based on the above, we use language in communication and language provides communication between the communicators. The resulting "speech" is the process of verbal communication. The most important thing is to set a clear goal for speech training and practice it. Without self-control, one can never master the culture of speech, the culture of behavior. The correctness of speech depends on its conformity to the norms of literary language.

References:

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3. "Psychology of communication and behavior" - Textbook, M. Nurmatova, 2016, Samarkand. p.114